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Investigation of potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASF) incursion in commercial pig herds in Romania

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Abstract

African swine fever (ASF), a severe viral disease affecting pigs, has been spreading in Europe since 2007. The first outbreak in Romania occurred in July 2017. The study aimed to investigate risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial domestic pig herds and the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of ASF and was coordinated by the National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority of Romania in cooperation with the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca and the Institute for Animal Health and Diagnosis. The study involved collecting data from pig farms (affected by ASF and matched control farms) and examining potential risk factors and vector involvement. The study employed a matched prospective case-control design. Data from ASF outbreaks reported to the Animal Disease Identification System (ADIS) and pig population data were used. Questionnaires were conducted on both ASF-case farms and control farms to identify potential risk factors such as farm density, proximity to wild boars, biosecurity measures, and farm management practices. Vector sampling focused on stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) and biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.). Traps were placed in strategic locations on farms, which were then tested in pools for ASF virus DNA. Out of 303 insect pools tested, 31 were positive for ASF virus DNA, all originating from case farms

where pigs were still present. Overall, 5 species of Culicoides were found positive for the ASFV DNA: *C. cataneii*, *C. longipennis*, *C. lupicaris*, *C. newsteadi* and *C. punctatus*. However, no virus has been successfully isolated from these positive samples. No control farms yielded positive results, and no stable flies tested positive for ASF virus DNA. The findings suggest a low risk of ASF dissemination by hematophagous insects. However, measures to limit insect access to farms and applying insecticides post-outbreak to prevent further spread are recommended.

Keywords: African swine fever, Romania, swine, vectors, mechanical transmission, risk factors

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1 Introduction

African swine fever (ASF) has spread among wild boar on the European continent, since it was first introduced in Georgia in 2007. From the introduction, the epidemic spread towards the north-east, and thereafter towards the west, entering the first EU Member States in 2014. The first outbreak of ASF in pigs in Romania was reported in July 2017 in the north-western part of the country. The first case of ASF in wild boars in Romania was confirmed in May 2018. Starting from June 2018, the epidemiological situation experienced a dramatic evolution, especially in the south-eastern region of the country, where, in a short period of time, many outbreaks were confirmed. The source of the virus is likely wild boar that migrated from Ukraine to the Danube Delta region of Romania (EFSA, 2018). The low level of biosecurity in backyard farms and the traditional socio-cultural particularities of the pig farming system in Romania facilitated the introduction of ASF virus in many holdings in a short period of time. ASF virus has mainly spread between holdings through the movement of pigs, meat products, people, vehicles and feed. High viral pressure combined with possible biosecurity breaches has led to the introduction of ASF virus into commercial farms. Currently, the entire territory of Romania is included in Part III of Annex I to Regulation (EU) 2023/594 and is subject to special disease control measures. The current project was developed in this context mentioned above.

In Romania, the project was coordinated by The National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority of Romania (hereinafter ANSVSA) in cooperation with the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca (hereinafter USAMVCN) and the Institute for Animal Health and Diagnosis (hereinafter IDSA).

The study had two specific objectives:

1. To investigate potential risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial domestic pig herds of different herd types and/or size;
2. To investigate the possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever.

Objective 1 was in the responsibility of ANSVSA, while objective 2 was in the responsibility of USAMVCN (vector sampling, vector identification, pooling) and IDSA (quantitative detection of the DNA of the African swine fever virus in the vector pools and identification of the swine blood meal source in the positive pools).

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor.

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: The National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority of Romania

Contractor/Beneficiary: EFSA

Contract/Grant title: Support to the Veterinary Services of Romania to investigate potential risk factors for African Swine Fever (ASF) incursion in commercial pig herds

Contract/Grant number: [GP/EFSA/ALPHA/2021/04](#)

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1.2 Data and methodologies

1.2.1 Data

Pig population data (commercial farms) were submitted to EFSA according to the population data model defined within the SIGMA project (EFSA, 2018b).

Data on ASF outbreaks in Romania reported to the Animal Disease Identification System (ADIS) were used in the study.

1.2.2 Methodologies

1.2.2.1 Potential risk factors for ASF incursion in domestic pig herds of different herd types and/or size

A matched prospective case-control design was used. For each outbreak farm, two control farms had to be randomly selected, matched by herd size and county. As soon as an outbreak was confirmed a case farm identification number was submitted to EFSA for random selection of control farms, using a random number algorithm, matched on county. From the list of eligible control farms, the first two on the list were called for the consent to participate in the survey and the actual number of pigs at the time of the outbreak. If there were no control farms available from the same category in the same county, a control farm in the neighbouring country was chosen.

When a suspicion of ASF appeared, this was also notified to the team involved in placing of the traps, to evaluate the risk of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever.

Accordingly, to the requirements of the EFSA grant, visual controls were performed on the farms where ASF was confirmed and on the matched control farms selected, to check if the answers in the questionnaire were correct and reliable. After completing the questionnaires, the information was introduced in EFSA database and analysed.

1.2.2.2 Possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever

Collection of vectors

We targeted to sample and examined two vector groups: stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) and biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.). The sampling protocol for each group is detailed in the following subsections.

Stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*)

The trapping method used for stable flies was based on sticky traps (EFSA 2017). We used commercial blue coloured traps. On each farm, two different locations were chosen. In each location, two traps were placed at a distance of 15 metres from each other in an area of expected heavy fly activity in direct sunlight to maximise visibility for stable flies. The traps were placed outside, near the animals, at a maximum height of 1.6 m. Traps were deployed for the whole duration of daylight, as stable flies are active during the day and attracted to translucent or blue-coloured objects.

All stable flies collected were kept dried and stored at -20°C during the shipment, for maximum 12 hours. Following this, the flies were kept at -80°C until they were morphologically identified and tested for ASFV DNA presence, blood meal source, and virus isolation.

Biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.)

The type of trap used for the collection of biting midges were the Mini CDC traps for *Culicoides* with UV light (Medlock et al. 2018). As suggested by Diarra et al. (2014), five such traps were placed per farm. The collection was done during the night as peak feeding times from April to October are between dusk and dawn. Traps were switched on 1 hour before sunset and switched off 1 hour after sunrise. The UV traps were placed at a standardised height: the UV tube has been placed at a height of 1.5 to 2 m from the ground (Diarra et al. 2014). Trapping was performed next to swine enclosures, in areas protected from wind and rain. The traps weren't placed near contaminating lights on the farms as this could affect the attraction of biting midges and their capture; traps were placed in dark spots.

Samples were stored dried after collection and kept at -20°C during transportation to the lab (max 12 h). At arrival, they were stored at -80°C, which facilitated the identification of *Culicoides* spp. (morphologically), the ASFV DNA, blood meal source, and virus isolation.

Identification of species

The identification of the insects was done on a morphological basis using a stereo zoom microscope. Identification was done based on one or more morphological characteristics: the general appearance (size, shape, colour), the shape or character of various body parts (antennae, legs, wings, bristles, other parts).

Stable flies (*Stomoxys calcitrans*)

Adults are basically grey in colour, with four black stripes on the thorax, and the abdomen is tessellated (checkered) in black. The extreme width of the frons and the characteristic markings on the abdomen are usually sufficient for the identification of these species. The size range is 4–7 mm for *S. calcitrans*. *Stomoxys calcitrans* greatly resembles the house fly *Musca domestica* to the untrained eye until one notices the sword-like proboscis projecting from beneath the head (Zumpt 1973; Foil and Hogsette 1994).

Biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.)

Culicoides identification was performed based on morphology (metric traits and wing pattern) using the Interactive Identification Key for Culicoides (IIKC), which currently includes 110 taxonomic units (102 species and 8 morphological variations) of biting midges (Mathieu et al. 2012).

Pooling

Prior to DNA extraction, pools were made, as described below. Each pool refers always only to insects belonging to the same species, collected on the same site and at the same sampling event.

A longitudinal dissection of every specimen was performed in order to obtain two identical halves of one individual. Consequently, we obtained two samples belonging to the same pool. One was used for the detection of ASFV DNA and pig DNA, and the other for further analysis, such as viral isolation.

Stable flies (*S. calcitrans*)

Due to size differences among the two insect groups, all collected stable flies were tested in pools of 2 specimens each.

Biting midges (*Culicoides* spp.)

All collected biting midges were tested in pools of 10 based (Cêtre-Sossah et al., 2004; Şevik & Oz, 2019).

Molecular protocol for ASFV DNA and pig DNA, including inclusion criteria for virus isolation

All collected biting flies (stable flies, biting midges) provided by USAMVCN were tested by PCR for ASFV according to the protocols used by ASF LNR of the Institute of Diagnostic and Animal Health (IDAH) on testing of ASF samples, respectively SOP Identification of the ASFV genome by real-time PCR based on the ASF EURL SOPs. Pooled samples were grounded in MagNa Lyser Green Beads with 1.5 ml of cold phosphate buffered saline (PBS1x) supplemented with 0.1% of antibiotic (gentamicin sulphate). Suspensions were clarified by centrifugation at 5,000 g for 5 min and 200 µl of the supernatant, which was used immediately for ASF virus and genome detection or stored at <-70°C until further use. For extraction and amplification steps, kits that have already been validated for routine detection of ASFV on animal samples, using the SOPs already in practice within the Romanian NRL for ASF, were used.

Detection of Pig (*Sus scrofa*) DNA

Blood meal analysis were conducted in order to evaluate if the vectors feed on pigs or on other hosts and to check if the ASFV DNA positive vectors have fed on pigs. However, the method is not able to distinguish between wild boars and domestic pigs. Nevertheless, wild boars were not present at the site of vector sampling during our work. Only pools positive to ASFV DNA were tested for the identification of pig DNA.

All positive samples for ASFV genome were tested by conventional PCR using an in-house method developed by the ASF NRL of the IDAH based on the protocol described by the Dalmaso A. et. al., A multiplex PCR assay for the identification of animal species in feedstuffs, Molecular and Cellular Probes 2004, 18:81-87.

Criteria for inclusion of pools for virus isolation trials

The identification of the ASFV genome was performed using a real-time PCR method. A Ct value was obtained for each positive sample. This value indirectly characterises the viral load, by providing quantitative data for the amount of ASFV DNA: the lower the value, the higher the DNA quantity. All samples which had a Ct value lower than 30 were submitted to The National Veterinary Research Institute in Poland (PIWET) for viral isolation trials.

2 Assessment/Results

2.1 Investigation of potential risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial domestic pig herds

To investigate potential risk factors for ASF introduction in commercial farms, a matched prospective case-control design was used.

Questionnaires were carried out both in ASF confirmed farms and also in two matched control farms.

With this approach, the following potential risk factors will be investigated:

- Pig/farm density,
- Distance to nearest outbreak in domestic farms,
- Distance to nearest wild boar case,
- Number of wild boar cases within a certain distance (reported to SIGMA)
- Wild boar density
- Lack of biosecurity measures implemented on the farm
- Type of feed, litter, drinking water provided to the pigs
- Potential environmental risk factors in the near surrounding of the farm
- Other potential farm management-related risk factors
- Potential transmission by arthropod vectors

A total of 72 commercial pig farms were visited of which 26 case farms (16 in 2021 and 10 in 2023) and 46 control farms (26 in 2021 and 20 in 2023). On 22 case farms both a questionnaire and vector survey were carried out, while on 2 case farms only a questionnaire and on 2 case farms only a vector survey were carried out. On the 33 control farms, both a questionnaire and a vector survey were carried out, while on the remaining 13 control farms only questionnaires were carried out.

In the figures below the location of the investigated commercial holdings, and the distribution of case and control farms can be seen.

As specified in Grant agreement, Romania (NSVFSA) had to carry on 25 questionnaires on the farms where ASF was confirmed and 50 questionnaires on the matched control farms in year 2023. In 2023, 10 ASF outbreaks in commercial holdings were reported in Romania and confirmed and 3 ASF outbreaks in type A commercial holdings (2 of them had less than 30 pigs in the holding). Romania performed 10 questionnaires on the farms where ASF was confirmed and 20 questionnaires on the matched control farms in 2023. All the farms that were confirmed with ASF were reported to EFSA in order to select the control farms. Only in 1 farm where ASF was confirmed, the economic operator refused to participate in the study,

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due to the fact that the farm is part of a consortium and had implemented very high biosecurity rules.

During the visits on the case and control farms, both a detailed questionnaire (see Annex 1), and entomological sampling was performed at the same time, immediately after the ASF outbreak was officially confirmed. (Tables/charts with Exploratory Analysis on Case-Control Study)

Figure 1. Numbers of farms involved in the study, split per category and per year.

Figure 2. Location of the case and control farms involved in the study.

2.2 Possible involvement of vectors in the transmission of African swine fever

Under the framework of the current project, samples were collected in case farms and control farms in 2021 and 2023. Overall, 72 farms were sampled as shown in Table 2.2.1. On two of the case farms and 13 of the control farms no vector surveys were carried out.

Table 2.2.1. Number of sampled farms per type (case/control) and year of study

Year	Case	Control	Total
2021	16	26	42
2023	10	20	30
Total	26	46	72

From these farms, a total number of 303 pools were prepared (Table 2.2.2).

Table 2.2.2. Number of pools prepared for each farms type (case/control) and year of study

Year	Case			Control			Total		
	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>
2021	124	19	105	46	24	22	170	43	127
2023	63	7	56	70	26	44	133	33	100
Total	187	26	161	116	50	66	303	76	227

Overall, 12 species of *Culicoides* have been identified (Table 2.2.3).

Table 2.2.3. Diversity of *Culicoides* and the respective number of pools by farm type and year of sampling

Species	2021			2023			Total		
	Case	Control	Total	Case	Control	Total	Case	Control	Total
<i>C. cataneii</i>	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	2
<i>C. circumscriptus</i>	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	2

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<i>C. fagineus</i>	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	2
<i>C. festiviipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
<i>C. longipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
<i>C. lupicaris</i>	4	0	4	0	0	0	4	0	4
<i>C. newsteadi</i>	32	8	40	17	6	23	49	14	63
<i>C. nubeculosus</i>	4	0	4	8	2	10	12	2	14
<i>C. obsoletus</i>	5	4	9	0	2	2	5	6	11
<i>C. pulicaris</i>	1	0	1	0	3	3	1	3	4
<i>C. punctatus</i>	57	7	64	27	30	57	84	37	121
<i>C. puncticollis</i>	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	2
Total	105	22	127	56	44	100	161	66	227

Out of the sampled farms, no target vectors (i.e. *Stomoxys*, *Culicoides*) were found in 5 farms in 2021 (one case farm and 4 control farms).

Stomoxys calcitrans was collected in 22 farms out of the 57 farms that were surveyed (Table 2.2.4).

Table 2.2.4. Number of farms where *Stomoxys calcitrans* was collected

Year	Case			Control			Total		
	Total	<i>S. calcitrans</i> found	<i>S. calcitrans</i> not found	Total	<i>S. calcitrans</i> found	<i>S. calcitrans</i> not found	Total	<i>S. calcitrans</i> found	<i>S. calcitrans</i> not found
2021	15	7	8	20	7	13	35	14	21
2023	9	1	4	13	7	6	22	8	14
Total	24	8	12	33	14	19	57	22	35

Culicoides spp. were collected in 38 farms out of the 57 farms that were surveyed (Tables 2.2.5-2.2.6).

Table 2.2.5. Number of farms where *Culicoides* spp. were collected

Year	Case			Control			Total		
	Total	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. found	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. not found	Total	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. found	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. not found	Total	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. found	<i>Culicoides</i> spp. not found
2021	15	9	6	20	12	8	35	21	14
2023	9	8	1	13	9	4	22	17	5
Total	24	17	7	33	21	12	57	38	19

Table 2.2.6. Number of farms where *Culicoides* spp. were collected, by species

Species	2021			2023			Total		
	Case	Control	Total	Case	Control	Total	Case	Control	Total
<i>C. cataneii</i>	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	2
<i>C. circumscriptus</i>	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	2
<i>C. fagineus</i>	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	2
<i>C. festiviipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
<i>C. longipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
<i>C. lupicaris</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>C. newsteadi</i>	5	5	10	6	5	11	11	10	21
<i>C. nubeculosus</i>	2	0	2	7	2	9	9	2	11
<i>C. obsoletus</i>	5	3	8	0	2	2	5	5	10
<i>C. pulicaris</i>	1	0	1	0	3	3	1	3	4
<i>C. punctatus</i>	7	5	12	7	7	14	14	12	26
<i>C. puncticollis</i>	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	2	2

Out of the 303 tested insect pools, 31 were positive for the DNA of ASFV. All of them originated in case farms and all of them in farms where the sampling was done while the pigs were still

present. No control farms yielded positive pools for ASFV DNA. No *Stomoxys* were found positive (Table 2.2.7).

Table 2.2.7. Number of positive pools/tested pools according to the insect group and the presence and absence of pigs in case farms

Year	Pigs present			Pigs absent			Total		
	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>	Total	<i>Stomoxys</i>	<i>Culicoides</i>
2021	23/123	0/18	23/105	0/1	0/1	0/0	23/124	0/19	23/105
2023	8/59	0/7	8/52	0/4	0/0	0/4	8/63	0/7	8/56
Total	31/182	0/25	31/157	0/5	0/1	0/4	31/187	0/26	31/161

Only *Culicoides* pools were ASFV DNA positive, with several species involved (Table 2.2.8).

Table 2.2.7. Number of pools and percent of ASFV DNA-positive pools of *Culicoides* collected from case farms in the presence of pigs, by species

Species	2021			2023			Total		
	Collected pools	Positive pools	%	Collected pools	Positive pools	%	Collected pools	Positive pools	%
<i>C. cataneii</i>	0	0	0	2	1	50.0	2	1	50.0
<i>C. circumscriptus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.0
<i>C. fagineus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.0
<i>C. festivipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.0
<i>C. longipennis</i>	0	0	0	1	1	100	1	1	100.0
<i>C. lupicaris</i>	4	1	25.0	0	0	0	4	1	25.0
<i>C. newsteadi</i>	32	5	15.6	16	3	18.8	48	8	16.7
<i>C. nubeculosus</i>	4	0	0	6	0	0	10	0	0.0
<i>C. obsoletus</i>	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0.0
<i>C. pulicaris</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.0
<i>C. punctatus</i>	57	17	29.8	26	3	11.5	83	20	24.1
Total	105	23	21.9	52	8	15.4	157	31	19.7

Overall, 5 species of *Culicoides* were found positive for the ASFV DNA: *C. cataneii*, *C. longipennis*, *C. lupicaris*, *C. newsteadi* and *C. punctatus*. However, this might be related to the low sample size in the case of the other species. Positive samples were detected in 4/9 case farms with *Culicoides* in 2021 and in 3/8 farms in 2023 (Total 7/17 case farms were *Culicoides* spp. were collected).

The Ct values for each positive sample are shown in table 2.2.8 together with the positivity for *Sus scrofa* DNA. Only the pools from two species of *Culicoides* yielded Ct values below 30, hence fulfilling the criteria for submission for the ASF virus isolation attempt: *C. newsteadi* (2/8 samples) and *C. punctatus* (8/20). Out the 31 ASFV DNA positive pools, all but one were positive also for *Sus scrofa* DNA.

Table 2.2.8. Number of pools and percent of ASFV DNA-positive pools of *Culicoides* collected from case farms in the presence of pigs, by species. Values in bold represent Ct values eligible for virus isolation attempt

Year	Species	Sample code	Ct value	<i>Sus scrofa</i> DNA	Virus isolation
2023	<i>Culicoides cataneii</i>	VI_2	37.32	positive	not tested
2023	<i>Culicoides longipennis</i>	VI_5	36.35	negative	not tested
2021	<i>Culicoides lupicaris</i>	2_17	30.24	positive	not tested
2023	<i>Culicoides newsteadi</i>	II_23	36.27	positive	not tested
2023		III_3	33.17	positive	not tested
2023		VI_1	32.79	positive	not tested
2021		2_7	33.45	positive	not tested
2021		2_35	35.60	positive	not tested
2021		4_4	36.30	positive	not tested

Risk factors for ASF in commercial pig herds in Romania

2021		4_11	25.60	positive	negative
2021		4_17	28.58	positive	negative
2023	<i>Culicoides punctatus</i>	II_4	29.39	positive	negative
2023		II_14	31.36	positive	not tested
2023		VI_3	33.37	positive	not tested
2021		2_12	32.76	positive	not tested
2021		4_3	28.76	positive	negative
2021		4_8	36.76	positive	not tested
2021		4_10	28.8	positive	negative
2021		4_23	32.46	positive	not tested
2021		4_24	38.01	positive	not tested
2021		5_13	33.58	positive	not tested
2021		5_15	30.87	positive	not tested
2021		5_17	36.76	positive	not tested
2021		5_18	30.07	positive	not tested
2021		5_20	27.24	positive	negative
2021		5_24	25.33	positive	negative
2021		5_25	28.09	positive	negative
2021		5_26	26.72	positive	negative
2021		5_27	31.57	positive	not tested
2021		5_28	26.89	positive	negative
2021		9_1	32.67	positive	not tested

3 Conclusion

The ANSVSA carried out on 25 questionnaires on the farms where ASF was confirmed and 50 questionnaires on the matched control farms investigating the potential risk for the incursion of ASF on commercial pig farms. In year 2023, Romania (ANSVSA) performed 10 questionnaires on the farms where ASF was confirmed and 20 questionnaires on the matched control farms in year 2023. All the farms that were confirmed with ASF were reported to EFSA in order to select the control farms. Only in 1 farm where ASF was confirmed the economic operator refused to participate in the study.

Due to the insufficient number of ASF case farms in Romania during the study period no conclusions could be made regarding risk factors for ASF incursion in commercial pig farms.

Although vectors were collected in all farms (case and control), the ASFV DNA was identified only in case farms and only when pigs were still present. Despite our previous results showed that ASFV DNA can be found in several vectors (i.e. *S. calcitrans*, *Culicoides* spp.) (Balmoș et al. 2021; 2023) or non-biting dipterans (Balmoș et al. submitted), our current study revealed positive sample only in the case of five *Culicoides* species, with two of them relevant (both regarding their relative abundance and the higher viral genome load Ct values): *C. newsteadi* and *C. punctatus*. However, generally the viral genome load in the positive samples was low and ASFV has not been isolated have been isolated from these.

4 Recommendations

Additional research is needed to investigate the risk factors contributing to ASF spread to fill in the gaps in knowledge concerning the major drivers leading to seasonality of ASF in the domestic pig populations.

To increase the sample size, results from two similar case-control studies that were performed simultaneously in Lithuania and Poland with the same study design shall be added in the analysis to potentially increase the power of the study for the three countries.

Considering that the virus was not isolated from any of the samples and that the persistence of the viral DNA in vectors seems to be limited in time, we consider that the risk of dissemination of ASF by hematophagous insects is low. However, we recommend measures for limiting the access of hematophagous insects to farms, using fine window meshes even for small insects such as *Culicoides* and application of insecticides also after the outbreak confirmation to limit the further post-outbreak spreading by insects.

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Annex A – Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Questionnaire on ASF in domestic pig farms in Romania/Lithuania/Poland

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this survey is to collect epidemiological data as well as any available information on the development of ASF in Romania/Poland/Lithuania to:

- Perform an analysis of the temporal and spatial patterns of ASF in domestic pigs, and
- Analyse the risk factors involved in the occurrence of ASF virus in **commercial pig farms**

INSTRUCTIONS

Please, carefully read the instructions before completing the questionnaire.

- A commercial pig farm is a holding where pigs are bred for commercial purposes. For this study, **only commercial pig farms of 30 or more pigs will be included.**
- Case (outbreak) farms will be farms where ASF has been confirmed.
- A list of 10 randomly selected control farms from the same county as case farm will be provided, matching on size (e.g. 30-200; 201-1000; >1000) each case farm. If a holding is selected as control holding, but preventive culling has been applied, or the control holding is suspected or has become (in the meanwhile) positive, please go to the next control holding on the list provided.
- High Risk Period (HRP) is defined as the length of time between possible introduction date and detection of the disease, during which no control measures have yet been implemented and disease continues to spread. To harmonize answers, we have arbitrarily defined a time lapse of 6 weeks.
- Note that you will be asked to provide the GPS location of the holding. Please, be equipped with a device that can retrieve this information (e.g. smartphone), or, if not possible to use a device, complete this information before the visit.

FIRST PART: TO BE FILLED IN BEFORE THE VISIT of the HOLDING by the **team member** appointed to perform the survey

* 1. Please, select your country:

- Lithuania
- Poland
- Romania

* 2. Full name of team member appointed to carry out the questionnaire:

* 3. Email address:

Information about the holding

* 4. Holding ID:

* 5. Disease status of pig herd

- Outbreak
- Control

* 6. If outbreak holding, kindly provide the date of ASF confirmation:

* 7. If control holding, kindly provide:

a. the case farm holding ID to which this control farm was associated

b. the date of the outbreak

* 8. Poland county (NUTS3) code:

SECOND PART: to be filled in DURING the visit

11. GPS coordinates (WGS84 coordinate system):

Example: Barcelona (Spain) has coordinates 41.403380 latitude, 2.174030 longitude

* Latitude

* Longitude

* 12. Date of the visit

Holding animals' information

* 13. Kindly provide the total number of pigs in the holding (all animals including sucklers):

* 14. Please, specify the number of each kind of pigs in the holding:

Small sucklers in farrowing boxes/pens (please provide an estimate if the exact number is not known):

* Weaned piglets (7-30 kg = piglets before they go to fattening)

* Breeding sows:

* Breeding boars:

* Fattening male pigs:

* Fattening female pigs:

* Fattening pigs (when sex is unknown):

* 15. Where are the pigs slaughtered?

- On the holding (including own slaughterhouse)
- In a contracted slaughterhouse
- No slaughter on farm (for example if they are all sold)

* 16. Does the farm owner have other pig farms?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, which is their holding ID?

* 17. Are there other animal species bred/kept IN the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine
- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits
- Other
- No other species

* If other, please, specify which and the number of each species:

* 18. Are there other animal species bred/kept OUTSIDE the pig holding?

More than one answer is possible

- Bovine
- Ovine
- Caprine
- Poultry
- Horses
- Pets (dogs, cats)
- Rabbits

- Other
- No other species

Wild boar information

* 19. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar or other pigs roaming near (i.e. within 100 m) your farm?

- Yes
- No

* 20. Did you ever notice crossbred pigs born in your holding?

- Yes
- No

* 21. Have you, or somebody else, ever seen a wild boar body / body remains in the vicinity of your farm?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, at what distance?

[please provide an estimate if you don't know the exact distance]

m

* 22. Could a wild boar access the feed storage?

- Yes
- No

* 23. Could a wild boar access the bedding storage?

- Yes
- No

* 24. Are there any attractive feed sources for wild boar (e.g. crops or trees) around/near (i.e. within 100 m) the holding?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify which type of feed source:

- Maize
- Fruit trees
- Oak trees
- Other

* 25. Is there any wild boar baiting or feeding site in the surroundings (i.e. within 100 m) of the farm (even if forbidden)?

- Yes
- No

Feed and drinking water

* 26. What type of feed is given on your holding?

More than one answer is possible

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- Industrial compound feed: mesh
- Hay
- Industrial compound feed: pellets
- Fresh grass
- Wet feed (for example buttermilk, whey)
- On-farm milling and mixture
- Cereals (including cereals used in your own on-farm milling and mixtures)

* Please specify the municipality/ies where cereals have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where hay have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* Please specify the municipality/ies where grass have been grown. If not known, write "I don't know"

* 27. Are there any signs of use of kitchen waste (to be answered by official vet)?

- Yes
- No

* 28. Do you feed kitchen waste (to be answered by farmer)?

- Yes
- No

* 29. What kind of drinking water is provided to the animals?

More than one answer is possible

- Fountain water (pumped from groundwater)
- Rain water stored in holding's own reservoir (e.g. tank, container, basin...)
- River/lake water
- Tap water (drinking / cleaning / disinfected water)

* If option 2 is selected, do wild boars have access to water reservoir?

- Yes
- No

Biosecurity

* 30. Did pigs have access to any type of outdoor areas on your holding within the last 6 weeks before the confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

- Yes
- No

* If yes, please specify the type of outdoor farm:

- Pigs have access to an outdoor area in forest, woodlands on agriculture land or pastures (see Figure 1 below)
- Pigs have access to an outdoor area on farm premises (adjacent to farm buildings) (see Figure 2 below)

Type of outdoor farm:

1

2

* 31. Did you introduce agriculture machinery and/or equipment potentially in contact with pigs within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

More than one answer is possible

- Yes, purchased new from dealer
- Yes, second hand or borrowed
- No

* 33. Is there a point of disinfection for the wheels at the entrance of the holding?

- Yes
- No

- * 34. How many visits of professionals on the holding (number of people entering the farm for professional reasons) occurred on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

Private veterinarians:

- * Official veterinarians:

- * Farm workers:

- * Consultants (industry reps...):

- * Suppliers of farm utensils/feed:

- * Live animal traders:

- * Others:

- * If OTHERS, please specify which:

- * 36. How many visitors (number of people belonging to family, friends, students, entering the farm for personal reasons) entered the holding on average on a daily basis within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

 visitors

- * 37. Was there any unusual event within the 6 weeks before the confirmation of the outbreak on the case farm/on the control farm corresponding to the case farm in case the interview is on a control farm?

More than one answer is possible

- Construction work new building
- Change of staff
- Family/social event
- Break in biosecurity routine

Risk factors for ASF in commercial pig herds in Romania

- Other
- No
- I don't know

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 38. What kind of bedding is used in the sheds?

More than one answer is possible

- Straw
- Wood chips
- Sawdust
- None
- Other

* If OTHER, please specify which:

* 39. Is the holding fenced to avoid contact with wild animals (e.g. wild boar, wolves, foxes, jackals...)?

- Yes
- No

* What type of fence?

- Double fence
- Solid single fence
- Single fence

* 41. Is manure from other holdings spread on neighbouring farmlands situated directly next to your stables (< 500 meters)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

* 42. Were NEW pigs and/or piglets introduced or purchased in the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm?

- Yes
- No

* 43. Were pigs sold from the establishment within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF on the case farm (or the corresponding case farm in case the interview is on a control farm)?

- Yes
- No

* 44. Were there any possible contacts with case farms within the 6 weeks before confirmation of ASF

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on the case farm? (e.g. natural mount, artificial insemination, shared material/objects/vehicles, external visitors, etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure/I do not know

* If yes, please specify the type of contact (e.g. vehicles, people, equipment...):

* 45. Does anyone among the workers of your holding carry out any outdoor activity (in wild boar habitat)?

More than one answer is possible

- Work (forest management, agricultural activities, bee-keeping, ...)
- Leisure (hiking, mountain climbing, mountain biking, bird watching...)
- Hunting
- None of the above I don't know
- Other

* If other, please specify which:

* 46 . Are the workers allowed to bring their own food in the holding?

- Yes
- No

* 47. Does anyone among the workers of your holding have contact to pigs on other farms or in their private life (including other premises owned by you)?

- Yes
- No

* 48. Can carcasses be collected by the rendering company from the public road, without entering to the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 49. Can the feed be delivered from the public road without entering the premises?

- Yes
- No

* 50. How are pigs loaded, when they leave for selling or slaughter?

- Truck enters farm and pigs can possibly return to shed from the truck
- Truck enters farm and pigs cannot return to shed from the truck
- Truck does not enter farm and pigs cannot return to shed

- * 51. Are pig pens accessible to visitors and workers only through the locker room?
 - Yes
 - No
- * 52. Is there a rodent control management plan implemented?
 - Yes
 - No
- * 53. Are there intact insect nets placed in front of the air intakes and the windows in the sheds?
 - Yes, on all air intakes and the windows
 - Yes, but not on all air intakes and the windows
 - No

* If yes, please provide the approximate mesh diameter:

mm

- * 54. Do you apply insecticide in or around your pig shed?
 - Yes
 - No
- * If yes, when was an insecticide last applied? (number of days since last application)

days

* 55. What product is used for disinfection of baths/ boot washers/stables at the holding?

Name of commercial product

- * 56. Is a quarantine period respected if new pigs arrive or are purchased in your holding?
 - Yes
 - No
- * If yes, how many days?

days

- * 57. Is the procedure all-in/all-out for all pigs on farm implemented?
 - Yes
 - No

Seasonality

- * 58. Do you share any crop harvesting machinery with other pig farmers?
 - Yes
 - No
- * 59. Is there a change in diet of the pigs over summer?
 - Yes
 - No

* If yes, please specify ...

Open question for case farms

* 60. Is there any other potential risk factor that we did not inquire about, that you consider the possible reason of introduction of the virus on your farm?

Background Documents

[Data Protection Note \[ENG\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[LT\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[PL\]](#)

[Data Protection Note \[RO\]](#)